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THE MIDDLE CLASS'S LOST AGENCY

Gitnang Uring Pantasya and Politics Post EDSA
EXCERPTS FROM UNPUBLISHED DISSERTATION

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This zine is made from the first chapter of a working dissertation by
Jong Malabed for the Doctoral Degree of Philosophy in UP Diliman.

The rest of the part and chapters are as follows:

2. Fantasy: Gitnang uring pantasya

What is middle class? Or, is Boni (and the Katipunan) middle class?/ The Cory fantasy and trapolitics/ The middle class's lost agency and the middle class's Other

3. Enjoyment: Walang basagan ng trip

The reality of middle class fantasy 1: Enjoy the economy stupid!// The reality of middle class fantasy 2: Enjoy the nation as yourself!// The reality of middle class fantasy 3: Enjoy Duterte!

4. Subject: Pag-asa ng bayan

Is there a subject please?/ The void of the middle class: OFWs and Empire, Tayo before the nation, Waiting for Benedict Anderson's Pinoy anarchist/ After Revolt and Pasyon: Nasan na ang masa!?

Conclusion

Politics: Ang kalayaan ay ginagawa (Politics after the event/ Can the event be forced?/ Politics in anticipation of an event)

In the shadow of a nascent tyrannical rule, the *event* of 1986 EDSA revolution has come full circle: from an overflowing mass of people crashing against the hostile machinery of a dictatorship to a trickle of protesters fighting against the spectral remains¹ of the former dictator. Perhaps it is fitting that the sustained share of this protest occurs in the simulated world of social media –after all, the then despot Marcos now exists mostly as simulacra.

Along the way, the act of freedom that was the first EDSA became an annual celebration that reduced it into a spectacle: something that we watch rather than do. And the people that was the subject of an overwhelming and transforming power was split, first, in EDSA 2 and, then, in the disavowed EDSA 3. What is left is the *middle class* frantically grasping for the now untenable fundamental *fantasy* of its lost agency, and nostalgic for that impossible *subjectivity* of immense power on the verge of creating a new world.

But the potential of EDSA to transfigure the then political into *a politics*, new and implacable, was coterminous with the act. It dissipated as soon as a new regime of the political was constituted. People power became mundane state power, wielded by a new configuration of elite –shifting but entrenched, buttressed by structures imposed and then ado/aped in a history of colonialism after colonialism and the neocolonial aftermath. The demand for vengeful justice was subsumed into numerous court cases helpless against the plodding process of the law. Most of what was pilfered was not recovered.² The victims of Martial Law never did get their due. And *Martial Law itself, the kernel and logic of the state* ubiquitously deployed in every experience of police discretion, continuously lurks in the shadows of our putatively restored democracy, repeatedly rearing multiple horrific heads.

EDSA, meanwhile, survives as sign and traces in the *symbolic* that evoke nostalgia. It also survives as fantasies that sustain intermittent movements that were already defeated even before they begun: EDSA 2, EDSA 3, the mass support for the dream presidency of FPJ, the fight against the sleaze and perversion that is the GMA regime, the underwhelming crowd of Luneta gathered against corruption in the form of the pork barrel during the previous administration, and the whimper against the policy of extra-judicial killings of the tyrant-in-making Duterte, but currently waylaid by the fight against an enemy that is already dead.

The middle class is what remains of the *people* of the EDSA “people power.” From our standpoint, the *masses* that supported Erap and then FPJ now appears to be living up to its name: politically indiscernible, fractured into many weak subjectivities, incapable of agency. The elite, meanwhile, are back in their privileged niche in the schema of *the political*. Only the middle class remains, so much so that it claimed EDSA as its own to the exclusion of all others –EDSA retroactively became largely a revolt of the middle class.³

This is the fantasy of the left behind trying to ignore the empty place of what is glaringly absent: the elections of our restored democracy will set things right. After all, was not EDSA setting an election right? Cory Aquino became the symbol of this hope, so much so that in death she breathed life into the political career of her mediocre son. And if elections fail, maybe another EDSA will set things right?

The second EDSA, properly middle class, ended a corrupt government and inadvertently, or so it slowly appeared, installed a worst one. Then, fearing the anticipated incompetence of a messianic movie actor and his huge mass support, we turned a blind eye to massive cheating in the elections and allowed the

¹ Cepeda, Mara. 2016. “‘Replica’ left in mausoleum on day of Marcos burial,” *Rappler*. Accessed December 18, 2016. <http://www.rappler.com/newsbreak/inside-track/152973-replica-body-mausoleum-marcos-burial>

² Davies, Nick. 2016. “The \$10bn question: what happened to the Marcos millions?” *The Guardian*. Accessed December 10, 2016. https://www.theguardian.com/world/2016/may/07/10bn-dollar-question-marcos-millions-nick-davies?CMP=share_btn_fb

³ See for example Rivera, Temario C. 2011. “The Middle Classes and Democratization in the Philippines: From the Asian Crisis to the Ouster of Estrada,” in *Southeast Asian Middle Classes: Prospects for Social Change and Democratization*, Edited by Abdul Rahman Embong. Bangi: Penerbit Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, 230-261. See also Pinches, Michael. 2010. “The making of middle class civil society in the Philippines,” in *The Politics of Change in the Philippines*. Edited by Yuko Kasuya and Nathan Gilbert Quimpo. Manila: Anvil, 284-312; and Rafael, Vicente. 2016. “The cellphone and the crowd: Messianic politics in the EDSA II uprising,” in *Motherless Tongues: The Insurgency of Language amid Wars of Translations*. Quezon City: Ateneo de Manila Press

the government to stand for six more years of questionable legitimacy.

This is the fantasy of the desperately rationalizing ad hoc and post hoc: the institutions of our democracy –the free press, the three branches of government, the constitution, etc., will tide us over until the coming of the true democratic leader that will break us out of our political impasse. Not PNoy, we now know.

Duterte is legitimately elected. More than 5000 people are killed. More turn up dead and cardboard memed everyday complete with hashtags and the macabre but strangely fitting witticisms.⁴ The former dictator –wax counterfeit and carcass, putrefaction arrested by preservatives –in being buried, comes back to haunt us. And our democratic institutions are either complicit or helpless. And we, though embattled, are complicit with our perverse *enjoyment*.

This is the fantasy of the possibly *impossible subject*: the healthy and growing economy will make us all middle class. And, happily, the economically invested and hopeful are, more often than not, liberals or democrats or both.

The *gitnang uri* of this *pantasya*, in the midst of mounting inequality within a global “patrimonial capitalism,”⁵ is tragically pathetic: always precariously on the verge of becoming poor, always frustrated, always melancholic,⁶ always fractured, always barred. And we, the middle class, elected and unwittingly sustain the current illiberal and undemocratic regime.

That the *political is doubled* is what is exposed when the fabric of middle class fantasy is inadvertently lifted or becomes tattered. On the one hand is the notional (or ideal) democratic politics collectively imagined in EDSA but now separately hoped for every national election thereafter. And on the other hand is its obscene double, what we customarily refer to as traditional politics. The pairs of this doubled political are mutually dependent. The democratic double performs an ideological function –it masks, it rationalizes when it can't hide. It sways and makes us complicit. The obscene double underpins the former –it is how things are done on the ground, it is the spit in *quid pro quo* handshakes, the unsaid in every clientelistic pat of the back. It is the realpolitik underneath all political discourse.

But the collective *imaginary* of EDSA was more than this obscuring or rationalizing ideology of the traditional political norm. EDSA was more than the Aquinos, more than the Catholic church and its faithful, more than the military coup, more than the fringe participation of the left. EDSA was more than the sidelined old elite, the middle class, and the poor who thronged and rebelled. EDSA was more than its individual parts, more than the sum of its parts. EDSA was a people aware of itself as such. And thus EDSA was the *real*. EDSA was *free*. And thus EDSA was power.

Like all of our revolutions, EDSA is unfinished. As an event, it needed and needs a politics that will generate its *truths*. In this, we have failed and continue to fail. Instead, what we have is an EDSA that has been appropriated by the political. And the political dominates its truth.

Fortunately, the current face of the political is neither compatible with EDSA's singular nor its appropriated form. Though despairing, we are living in an opportune time. In this crisis there appears three possibilities (but only one opens the possibility for the entirely new) for the middle class –the default champion of the EDSA that was –within the horizon of its fantasies: 1.) Continue as we are. Protest within the political and aim to influence policy. Maybe we can be granted the exhumation of a dead enemy. Maybe we can reconcile the EDSA of our imagination with the present *situation*. Maybe we can live contentedly within the doubled political if we can make our democratic ideals potent again. 2. Claim EDSA so thoroughly in such a way that we will our particularity into the universal. The middle class will either represent or subsume all other positions within a politics that will seek to capture the political. Or, 3.) We let go of the political altogether and engage in a politics –here, we may find the past companions we have lost and, perhaps, in struggling together against the *state of the situation* we can constitute an immanent excess of great potency –a new people.

UPLB, November 2016

⁴ Evangelista, Patricia. 2016. “Impunity: Murder as meme,” *Rappler*. Accessed December 18, 2016. <http://www.rappler.com/newsbreak/in-depth/154193-impunity-drugs-crime-murder-meme>

⁵ See Piketty, Thomas. 2014. *Capital in the twenty-first century*. Translated by A. Goldhammer. London: The Belknap Press of Harvard University Press

⁶ See Tolentino, Rolando B. 2010. *Gitnang Uring Pantasya at Materyal na Kahirapan sa Neoliberalismo: Politikal na Kritisismo ng Kulturang Popular*. Manila: University of Santo Tomas Publishing House

precarious middle class life. Drug users and pushers are the extreme manifestation of the poor's unruliness, which menace the middle class' and elite's law abiding and peaceful existence.¹²⁶ But the fundamental fantasy of our lost agency remains operative as we look toward Duterte and his drug war to alleviate our oppressive inertness: either as stand in for what we misplaced or as adversary that will finally summon our will to fight.

Meanwhile, within the horizon of the philosophies/theories already laid out, we know that the void of the subject becomes a social anxiety in times of crisis. And historically, post-EDSA, we know that we always turn away from the abyss of freedom that is the subject and instead depended on the Other (the state and its series of would be messiahs) for our deliverance. And what is political crisis if not the crisis of our enjoyment, whether political, economic, or cultural.

These beg more questions: What is the nature of the crisis of our enjoyment that made the middle class turn to the version of the political that Duterte offered and is delivering? What is the nature of our current enjoyment that is now administered by the new authoritarian arrangement? The fatasmatic specter that prevents us from enjoying or that endangers our enjoyment has always been an essential part of middle class fantasy: Marcos for Cory, FPJ and the ignorant masses for GMA, GMA for Pnoy...How do the fantasmatic specter of the narco-state and the fanstamatic bogey of the former dictator, nightmarish fantasies of the middle class both, relate to each other? How do their dynamics structure our contemporary social reality?

And finally: What politics can measure up to current state of the situation? Can this politics still generate truths from the event that was EDSA? Or has there been a new event from which a new politics can draw its truths? Do we need to wait for this new event? Can we force it? What is the subject of this event's new and adequate politics? What are its truths?

*Ay! Bugtong, bugtong
Huwag nang lilingon
Nasa iyo ang tugon:
Anong munting kasinungalingan
Ang damuhalang katotohanan?*

This philosophical research will be about Philippine politics post-EDSA as structured by middle class fantasy. It will be about how middle class fantasy sustained the varying appearances of the political since 1986 and how it continues to sustain the current political arrangement that seem to assault its foundations. I will seek to question these contents through the theoretical concepts of event, ideology, and subjectivity.

As metapolitics, as the seizing of the truths of EDSA generated through middle class politics, this research work is also envisioned as an intervention along the lines of a politics still to be thought out.

The text is divided into four parts with three chapters each. The first part is about EDSA as an event. It asks the basic questions: Anong meron? Anong nangyari? The first chapter, “Beyond Marcos and Martial Law is the logic of the state of exception,” discusses the state of the situation before EDSA. It argues that the state of the situation was the state of exception, and that the state of exception is only minimally different to the event that overturned it. The second chapter, “Minimal difference: EDSA as an event,” explains the people power revolution along Badiou's theory of the event by reading through remembrances and the many rethinking of EDSA. The third chapter, “Eraserheads, FPJ, and the split ‘people.’” follows through with a theorizing of how the “people” of EDSA's people power split into the subjectivities that laid claim to the event. It does this through readings of the sensation of the Eraserheads as Real OPM that evokes the unity that was EDSA, and of the phenomenon of the messianic actor and would-be-president FPJ whose life and death reveals the trajectory of the masses' political fate within the political.

2016. <http://www.rappler.com/nation/155905-lawmakers-president-duterte-reveal-medical-status>

¹²⁶ See Jerusalem, Jigger. 2017. “Duterte to poor: ‘If you die, I'm sorry,’” *Inquirer.net*. Accessed March 26, 2017. <http://www.newsinfo.inquirer.net/883818/duterte-to-poor-if-you-die-im-sorry>

politics came straight from the horse's mouth when Senator Jinggoy Estrada stood up in a privilege speech to denounce the discriminatory application of justice, revealing in the process that all senators who confirmed the impeachment of the Chief Justice received (or were promised) additional 50 million pesos of PDAF by the administration.¹²¹

At this point, Duterte begs more questions than answers

Middle class fantasy works because it is our fantasy. The doubled political works because it is middle class politics, it is our politics. We consent to it by denying its obscene underside, by consoling ourselves that we can choose otherwise, and by accepting the bribe of the putative post-ideological world: that we can enjoy without the guilt.¹²²

Using Zizek's philosophical concepts, we can gather the disparate real life examples of the fair-trade Starbucks coffee, the proxy-violence of boxing, and the doubled character of Philippine politics under the banner of ideology: (1) Recent fair-trade discourse raises concern for the human cost of exploitative coffee production. But it is also a great marketing strategy that solves the bitter taste of guilt that it fosters. Fair-trade Starbucks coffee is more expensive precisely because it is claimed to be fair-trade. Does the coffee being fair-trade help solve global poverty and mitigate the harsh life of farmworkers? Well, not really. We know that it will take more than fair trade to make their world a better place. But we can enjoy our coffee precisely because of the fair-trade claim. What we buy with the fair-trade logo is guilt-free enjoyment. (2) What about Manny Pacquiao? Whenever he fights he says that he fights for every Filipino. We believe we are Filipinos but we rarely can give an account of how being a Filipino feels. Nation is a chore to imagine and we normally don't. But, early in his career before his transformation into a standard politician, each time Pacquiao fought we felt that indeed we were Filipinos. We enjoyed the nation/-state as ourselves. We also enjoyed violence, the kernel of the nation-state's power, in each bloody fight (and through every punch Pacquiao threw). (3) And our politics? Well we know very well that traditional politics is how our notional democracy does politics on the ground but we believe and behave as if they are opposed, that someday democracy will triumph and that we will finally get rid of traditional politics. The point of this entire charade is for us to enjoy our politics now, and to enjoy it as the political.

But what about the current neo-fascist Duterte regime? What is its connection to middle class politics? Does not the current politics of death contradict the middle class fantasy of democratic politics? Does the doubled political still hold? Did change indeed come so that there is a new middle class fantasy organizing our politics?

That Duterte had the overwhelming support of the middle class and the elite prior to the 2016 election is clear. In a survey conducted by Pulse Asia in November 2015, he received his highest support from the ABC class, 62 percent compared to his support from the D and E classes, 37 percent and 32 percent.¹²³ That Duterte continues to enjoy this support is also clear four months after taking over the presidency with 86 percent approval rating despite the extrajudicial killings of suspected drug users and dealers in the thousands.¹²⁴ The ghastly irony is that Duterte himself admits to abusing painkillers more powerful than morphine.¹²⁵

Currently, middle class politics has shifted with Duterte's presidency. In the doubled political, democratic ideals are ridiculed and are replaced with the ideal of lawful order. And such lawful order is going to be achieved extrajudicially. The drug war is this doubled political's form: Drug users will be killed to save the nation. It is Duterte's own personal martial law. To some extent the economic form of the of the *gitnang uring pantasya* becomes more relevant. In Duterte's narrative, the drug problem threatens the

¹²⁰ See Go, M.G.A. 2011. "Deals pork behind impeach votes," in *Newsbreak*. Accessed December 10, 2016.

<http://www.newsbreak.ph/2011/03/22/belmonte-carried-the-show-for-lp/>

¹²¹ InterAksiyon. 2013. "The untold PDAF story that people should know." *InterAksiyon.com*. Accessed December 10, 2016.

<http://interaksyon.com/article/71508/jinggoy-estrada-privilege-speech--the-untold-pdaf-story-that-people-should-know>

¹²² Zizek 2005b, 250-251

¹²³ GMA News. 2015. "Duterte leads SWS Nov. 2015 poll." *GMA News Online*. December 7. Accessed December 10, 2016.

<http://www.gmanetwork.com/news/story/546994/news/nation/duterte-leads-sws-nov-2015-poll/>

¹²⁴ See Dioquino, Rose Ann. 2016. "Duterte scores 86 percent approval, trust ratings in Pulse Asia survey," *GMA News Online*. Accessed December 10, 2016. <http://www.gmanetwork.com/news/story/584708/news/nation/duterte-scores-86-percent-approval-trust-ratings-in-pulse-asia-survey>

¹²⁵ "He however said his doctor made him stop using it on learning he was 'abusing the drug' by using more than the prescribed patches." The "drugs" referred to here is a prescription painkiller 100 times more potent than morphine. See

Aeance France-Presse. 2016. "Lawmakers to Duterte: Reveal your medical status." *Rappler*. Accessed: December 18, 2016.

A metapolitics para sa bayan nating sawi

Alain Badiou, in the first essay of his book *Metapolitics*,⁷ asks: "What is political philosophy?" His answer, that it is a "programme which, holding politics –or, better still, the political –as an objective datum, or even invariant, of universal experience, accords philosophy the task of thinking it" also identifies the political philosopher as someone who enjoys the triple advantage of, first, being the analyst and thinker of "this brutal and confused objectivity" in lieu of "real instances of politics;" second, being the priest of the good politics that "conform[s] to ethical demands" and; third, being the one excused from any politics at all. Here, philosophy and philosopher both work to restore politics to the free exercise of "judgment in a public space where, ultimately, only opinions count" and where truth is exiled.⁸

Except for the rather contentious parts regarding philosophers being above politics and the exile of truth, from the point of view of philosophy and the philosopher, the above general description of political philosophy is, more or less, traditionally unproblematic and commonplace. But, of course, the exempt parts are kernels of certain positions within philosophy. We can imagine, for example, Hannah Arendt⁹ and Michel Foucault¹⁰ objecting to the first exception but agreeing with the second for different reasons. They represent strands of contemporary philosophy that question philosophy's relation to truth. This questioning reveals a positioning that is very much a politics and places them within its practice. Meanwhile, we can also imagine Thomas Hobbes¹¹ and Carl Schmitt,¹² or even John Rawls¹³, insisting on the truth of their political philosophies from the positions they take vis-à-vis what Schmitt designates as the "political," precisely what Hobbes rationalizes as the Sovereign or what Rawls identifies as "political justice," that essentially wills and judges for all. And they insist on this not politically but theoretically, from a standpoint above the fray.

Against these positions within philosophy, and against political philosophy,¹⁴ Badiou deploys the concept and practice of *metapolitics*—the thinking of a politics whose truths necessarily politicizes philosophy itself beyond the limits of what is customarily tolerable. It combines the two aversions of current political philosophy (of subjective political practice and truth) into militancy in politics that generates truths, and makes them constitutive of philosophical thought. This is, in effect, the contemporary application of Karl Marx's 11th thesis in his "Theses on Fierbach"¹⁵: "The philosophers have only interpreted the world, in various ways; the point, however, is to *change* it."¹⁶ But the relevance of this assertion to Marx's philosophy, and to Badiou's in the present-day, is only apparent when we understand it as embedded in Marx's first thesis, which criticizes all "existing materialism" of his time for the "chief defect" of thinking that "the thing, reality, sensuousness, is conceived only in the form of the object or of contemplation, but not as *human sensuous activity, practice, not subjectively*."¹⁷ This brings us back to metapolitics, which, as well as joining philosophy into practice and transforming it into politics as thought, also restores politics "to the subjective reality of organised and militant processes."¹⁸ But philosophy, here, is not subordinate to politics. Philosophy is an active seizing of the truths generated by politics, giving it space and freedom in thought. It is also reflecting, deliberating, deriving and generating values and meanings; it is systematizing, attaching time and freeing from time; it is thinking the conjuncture of truths.¹⁹

This tradition of militant thought or active philosophy is a defining character of Marxist philosophy that is continuously reworked. In between Marx and Badiou, Louis Althusser for example, defines philosophy as "theory of theoretical practice."²⁰ He argues that philosophical enquiry is necessary if

⁷ Badiou, Alain. 2005b. *Metapolitics*. London: Verso

⁸ Badiou 2005b, 10-11

⁹ Arendt, Hannah. 1968. "Truth and politics," in *Between Past and Future*. New York: Pantheon Books

¹⁰ Foucault, Michel. 1984. "Truth and power," in *The Foucault reader*. Edited by Paul Rabinow. New York: Pantheon Books

¹¹ Hobbes, Thomas. 2000. *Leviathan*. Edited by Richard Tuck. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press

¹² Schmitt, Carl. 1996. *The concept of the political*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press

¹³ Rawls, John. 1993. *Political liberalism*. New York: Columbia University Press

¹⁴ Badiou's heading for the first essay in his book

¹⁵ Marx, Karl. 1978. "Theses on Feuerbach," in *The Marx-Engels reader*. Edited by Robert

¹⁶ Tucker. New York and London: W. W. Norton & Company. 143-145

¹⁷ Marx 1978, 143; emphases in Marx

¹⁸ Badiou 2005b, 10

¹⁹ Badiou, Alain. 1999. *Manifesto for philosophy*. Translated and Edited by Norman Madarasz. Albany: State University of New York Press, 37-38

²⁰ See Althusser, Louis. 1969. *For Marx*. Translated by Ben Brewster. London: NLB

also Althusser, Louis. 1970. *Reading Capital*. Translated by Ben Brewster. London: NLB

Marxism is to transcend the then political impasse that trapped it: “Philosophy is a certain continuation of politics... [it] represents scientificity in politics, with the classes engaged in the class struggle” or more simply, “[p]hilosophy is, in the last instance, the class struggle in theory.”²¹

In fact, Badiou’s metapolitics owes its singularity by its link and eventual release from the bounds of Althusser’s philosophy. For Badiou, philosophy is not theory but “a thinking of the distinctions in thought,” distinctions that “verify the ‘shifting’ of the political condition.” It has no political object (and thus, not really science). It is an activity that has immanent effects: the “discovery of new possibles *in actu*” for politics. Philosophy, in effect, frees politics from history: it “authorizes a non-historicist perception of political events.”²² As politics is not something we know but something we do, metapolitics allows the thinking of politics not as cause or effect but rather as singular, but also as generic.

This idea and practice of metapolitics is not really completely foreign to Philippine political experience. The most relevant and exemplary is Albert Alejo’s *Tao po! Tuloy!*,²³ which elides the Marxist tradition in order to find an indigenous motivation for subjective militant thought. Alejo reveals that his book’s publication was delayed by five years when it was finally printed in 1990. This means that he wrote his philosophy of *loob* during the height of the struggle against Martial Law and immediately before the EDSA revolution. “*Sakit ng kalingkingan/ Damdam ng buong katawan.*”²⁴ This is the proverb that Alejo uses as an epigraph for the first section of his book. Within the closely following text, he cites another aphorism – “*Hampas sa kalabaw, sa kabayo ang latay*”²⁵ – to underpin the founding questions for his philosophy: What connects him to the daily struggles of his fellows within the context of the greater struggle for dignity and freedom? Why does he willingly entangle himself in the strivings of others? And why do others involve themselves as willingly as he does? These questions are prompted by an urge to philosophize in the calm between fatigue and rest – when the experiences of the day are still manifest on the body that has, at the same time, withdrawn from direct political action. Alejo is sure that the answer is not as simple as “ideology.” Instead, both the urge to philosophize and the still opaque answer to his questions emanate from a feeling he describes as “*pagkabalisa ng loob.*”²⁶ He knows that he is connected to his fellows because nababalisa ang kanyang loob. He cannot resist the call to philosophize because *nababalisa ang kanyang loob*. But what is “loob”? It is certainly not a simple object of a philosophical questioning as it is present in him as it is in others. Loob is both experience and practice that is very much entangled with his politics. Loob, in Alejo’s case, is a questioning. The quest to understand this is the quest to understand his involvement in both the ordinary and the great strivings of his people. It is also the quest to generate the truth of his and his fellows’ struggle.

This is what I strive for in this work: a metapolitics for the event and after event that was the fruition of the struggles of Alejo’s generation – a *metapolitics of EDSA and its after*. But what he dismisses or evades I must confront, as I see it as the crucial philosophical concept that can clear the intoxicating miasma of our contemporary politics. Contra-Alejo then, it is “ideology” or, to be more current, *fantasy*. And to engage this concept I need to return to singular appearances of what has been designated as Marxist philosophy, albeit rather very narrow and focused readings. The earlier introductory section, which analyzes EDSA vis-à-vis the middle class and its fantasies, is a barebones metapolitics still to be fleshed out. Within it are *bold italicized* words that are philosophical concepts masquerading, but mostly failing, as ordinary terms within an aspiring but barely active philosophical text. The first move for this hopefully militant work then is to review these concepts as contextualized within a larger conversation in the philosophy of politics and as entangled within the range of existing politics *ng bayan nating sawi*.

Tinimbang ka ngunit kulang

As a concept and a practice, metapolitics depends upon the distinction Badiou makes between the political and a politics. The political is linked with the politics of the state, which, to Badiou’s (and to the typical) experience, is parliamentary politics in the era of neoliberal economies. As such, the political is characterized by political representations of

²¹ Althusser, Louis. 1971. *Lenin and philosophy and other essays*. Translated by Ben Brewster. London: Monthly Review Press, 64-65

²² Badiou 2005b, 61-63

²³ Alejo, Albert. 1990. *Tao po! Tuloy!: Isang Landas ng Pag-unawa sa Loob ng Tao*. Quezon City: Office of Research and Publications, Ateneo de Manila University

²⁴ Alejo 1990, 3

²⁵ Alejo 1990, 5

²⁶ Alejo 1990, 4-5, 116-117

In our doubled politics, we can think of Cory Aquino (and Ninoy) as symbolizing the rational hope for a democratic politics. We are socialized into this hope from our grade school social studies and history subjects to our college liberal education. We inaugurated this hope into a national aspiration through the 1986 EDSA revolution. Cory, beyond death, embodies this democratic possibility for our politics. Meanwhile, we can think of GMA as symbolizing the disavowed double of Philippine democratic politics: hello Garci, her husband’s syndication of government corruption, her lavish dinners, spiteful SONA, scandals (obscene in so many ways), scams – all indicators of her embeddedness in traditional political culture. GMA is Cory’s obscene double. Both are placed in the apex of Philippine politics by people power, the two EDSAs seen as uprisings of the middle class, but ended symbolizing its opposite possibilities. GMA is people power’s ironic twist, the embodiment of its extreme possibility: a neo-authoritarian figure of democracy’s excess.

To some extent, Noyon Aquino saved us from a very possible political implosion and returned us to the politics before GMA. Cory’s death made his candidacy in the 2010 elections possible. We imagined him as representing, and thus substituted him for, the democratic icons that were his parents. His election and post-election rhetoric of “*kayo ang boss ko*” and *daang matuwid* set on the right track our doubled politics that got derailed by the crisis that was GMA. We can disavow again! GMA and her ilk still dominated Congress after the 2010 elections? Well, all became well with the impeachment of then Ombudsman Merceditas Gutierrez and Chief Justice Renato Corona. Senators, congressmen and countless local politicians plundered the nation’s treasury through Janet Napoles’ ingenious scheme of channeling pork barrel funds into bogus non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and foundations? All was well after the Supreme Court declared PDAF and other forms of pork in the national budget illegal and after some of these politicians were imprisoned. Our sovereignty endangered and our police/soldiers dying in a botched US sponsored operation to retrieve or kill terrorists listed in the American order of battle? All was well as suspended Police Chief and Pnoy bosom buddy, General Purisima, was finally fired from the PNP and as the many declared investigative bodies filed their reports incriminating even the President. We are desperate for the little of what is left of our ideal democratic politics to let us disavow what we know and always knew.

The documentation and analysis of deceit and hypocrisy in Philippine society is not something new. Jaime Bulatao, S.J.¹¹⁸ *split-level Christianity* to refer to the existence of two contradictory value system within individuals – wherein adherence to the Christian faith and values is professed while actual action or behavior is determined by contrary set of norms, beliefs, and ways of living that are primarily cultural and customary. In this particular duplicity, the Christian value system becomes an abstract construct, a notion or an ideal, that excuses, or that hides, actual conflicting behavior. Analogously then, we can think of Christian values as corresponding to ideal democratic politics, and the opposed customary behavior as akin to traditional politics. But, in Bulatao’s schema, the opposing values in split-level Christianity do not make a system. Eventually, customary values and their corollary behavior are chosen over Christian values in a “distancing” that sees it as unrealistic and thus justifiably violated. Or if the conflict is unresolved, it leads into a crisis that eventually destroys the individual and society.¹¹⁹

The political duplicity in Philippine doubled politics, on the other hand, is stable as both notional democratic politics and traditional politics makes a functioning system. At the beginning of the PNoy administration for example, the President represented the move to impeach then Ombudsman Gutierrez as a democratic goal. If she was out of the way then the cases of graft against officials of the previous administration will prosper, *daang matuwid* will move forward. The same rationalization and framing was used in the impeachment of Chief Justice Corona, also an appointee of GMA. But investigative reports on Gutierrez’s impeachment reveal that the ways and means of traditional politics were used to convince Congress to impeach the Ombudsman. Pork barrel, budget insertions, the immediate release of funds, etc. were promised and given to those who voted to impeach.¹²⁰ In the case of Corona, the workings of *trapo*

¹¹⁸ Bulatao, Jaime, S.J. 1996 (1966). “Split-level Christianity.” *Phenomena and their Interpretation: Landmark Essays 1957-1959*. Quezon City: Ateneo de Manila University Press.

¹¹⁹ Actually, Zizek’s analysis may work well with Bulatao. In recent Vatican politics, conservatives oppose the official acknowledgement of what is already practiced: that divorced or separated Catholics may go to confession and receive the holy sacrament. “For them, the gap between theory and practice is exactly what gives the church meaning.” See Brown, Andrew. 2017. “The war against Pope Francis.” *The Guardian*. Accessed October 27, 2017.

<https://www.theguardian.com/news/2017/oct/27/the-war-against-pope-francis/>

consumerism is also that of the poor, as Tolentino suggested.

Meanwhile, the mass support for FPJ in the 2004 elections was proof of the poor's belief in the middle class ideal of democratic elections and transition of power. Even EDSA 3 was in support of the then democratically elected president and, consequently, of the constitutional process. When middle class fantasy is the economic and political aspiration of the poor, it becomes effectively what the elite needs to justify and reproduce the state and its status quo. Middle class fantasy is, thus, for everyone.

If the kernel of middle class fantasy is its lost agency, then the state is the Other that has what it lost and that wields it for them. Elections ensure the succession of leaders amongst whom the nation waits for him who knows how what was lost can be restored. Thus, like Badiou, we can say that middle class fantasy is the ideology of the state of the situation. It is how it organizes the parts and subsets of a situation; it is how it re-presents their putative relations. And thus, like Žižek, we can also say that the middle class fantasy, as the fantasy of the whole and as the substitute for the sublime of the people, desires and knows itself through the state and its politics.

Žižek says that contemporary ideology works precisely by claiming that it is beyond ideological or that it is post-ideological. The liberal democratic ideology is thus the contemporary ideology par excellence in that it asserts itself as neutral and that it only provides the space for all other ideologies or worldviews to debate and influence governance. This stance, which is *fetishistic disavowal* in Žižekian terms, is also how the subjects of ideology relate to it and its order: "I know very well that it is not the case; nevertheless I believe that it is anyway."¹¹³ Here, we can reformulate Marx's "[O]ne man is king only because other men stand in the relation of subjects to him. They, on the other hand, imagine that they are subjects because he is king"¹¹⁴ into Žižek's "I know very well that [he] is king only because [we] other men stand in the relation of subjects to him, nevertheless I still 'imagine that [we] are subjects because he is king.'" Or in the case one issue that we have disavowed very effectively and as such forgotten: "We know very well that the pork barrel did not go away with the Supreme Court decision to ban its incarnation as PDAF, nevertheless we believe and act as if it is gone anyway, life goes on."¹¹⁵ The disavowal can also be expressed in the form of *ideological disidentification*; "Yes, I follow the law but I can also break it anytime I want," that is, the law's true effectiveness is not because it sanctions or prohibits but precisely because we believe that we are free even if we follow it. And in practice, the law gives us the leeway to enjoy its violation by sometimes looking away. And so we have our very own little suspensions of the law: jaywalking or running the red light, smoking in non-smoking zones, littering, taking or borrowing from office supplies, bribing to expedite government permits to fast track government services, etc. These are correlative to the state of emergency, the suspension of the law to protect the lawful order—the point is the order. To some extent, the law is also there to manage our enjoyment through its violation. This is because our enjoyment¹¹⁶ also sustains the order.¹¹⁷ Thus the organization of our enjoyment is the obverse of the law: it is the law's obscene double that delights in its disruption but, also precisely as such, that supplements its effectiveness.

This is the logic of middle class fantasy and its politics. But what exactly is the middle class fantasy as politics? How is it as a politics?

The politics of the middle class is the *doubled political*, it is the doubled politics of the state. First, it is doubled in the original Marxist sense of deception (a consequence of the simple notion of ideology as false consciousness); i.e., that there is something that is deliberately hidden. Second, it is doubled in the sense that what appears to be and what is hidden exist at the same time, parasitic on each other, constituting what we experience as the whole of Philippine politics. On the one hand is the notional or ideal democratic politics best exemplified by the promise of EDSA. On the other hand is its obscene double, what we usually refer to as traditional politics. The democratic double performs an ideological function—in the sense that it allows us to disavow the workings of its obscene double. The obscene double underpins the former and is the politics of the shadows that makes its democratic double work—in the sense that democratic goals are achieved through traditional political means. It was during the presidency of Gloria Macapagal-Arroyo (GMA) that the facade masking our *trapolitics* became completely transparent. The problem, of course, was that we couldn't properly disavow what was right in front of us. Corruption and scandals headlined newspapers, and TV and radio news almost daily. The hypocritical/cynical stance of fetishistic disavowal became untenable.

¹¹³ Žižek 1991, 73 and 241-242. See also Žižek, Slavoj. 2005. "Between symbolic fiction and fantasmatic spectre: Toward a Lacanian theory of ideology," in *Interrogating the real*, London and New York: Continuum

¹¹⁴ Marx, Karl. 1990. *Capital*, Volume 1. London, Penguin Classics, 149 n22

¹¹⁵ Torres-Tupas, Tetch. 2013. "SC declares PDAF unconstitutional," *Inquirer.net*. Accessed December 10, 2017. <http://www.newsinfo.inquirer.net/530223/sc-declares-pdaf-unconstitutional>

¹¹⁶ This includes the "*kasiyahan*" or enjoyment that Tolentino (2010) identified.

¹¹⁷ This is an argument of Žižek's 1991 book.

all sorts, administered and refined through putative democratic processes, and driven by the market of public opinion, which, ultimately, rationalizes the unitary acts of the state. But it is also a consequence of the anxieties of the minimal state in matters of both internal and global order and security that replaced the social/class antagonisms that hitherto provided the state with rationale in the period of planned or mixed economies.²⁷ The political, then, is not simply connected with the politics of the state vis-à-vis its changing concerns but also with the state itself, its rationale and its reason—what the earliest theorists of the state recognized as the "reason of state."²⁸

To some extent and much closer to home, this recalls Schmitt's concept of the political, which limits state politics to the determination of friends and enemies and to the actions required by such decisions.²⁹ This applies clearly and immediately to the externally displaced anarchic situation that describes the inter-state relations of alliances and wars post-Leviathan. But this also applies domestically, as Schmitt himself grapples with the problem posed by the liberal-parliamentary politics of the state, which appear to erode the capacity of the state for unitary action. This happens in two ways: (1) liberal-parliamentary politics muddies the properly political with social (and thus private) concerns, and (2) liberal-parliamentary politics paralyzes the state power of the "decision" through divisive debate and infighting.³⁰ Schmitt conceptually resolves the first by designating such purported political concerns as pre-political. Social concerns such as the economic, religious, associational, class, etc., are anathema to the political but they become political when advocates reach the decisive point of identifying enemies and fighting then so as to gain dominance over the political, as when Marxists take class antagonism to its conclusion by fighting the enemy class and controlling the state.³¹ And within the domain of an already existing political, when forces that want to take over its politics challenge the state, such forces can be declared as internal enemies and fought accordingly.³² But Schmitt has no answer for the second problem supposedly posed by liberal politics, which poses the danger of society taking over the state and eliminating the political altogether. History, of course, has shown that Schmitt was hasty. Liberal democracies fight and has fought countless wars and they win. The decision to go to war, while more demanding in liberal states, is enabled by its structures of representation that limit the determining debate to the few, and the decision to one.

The liberal decision is also facilitated by norms or rules that limit debates to the "reasonable," thus preempting liberal plurality's supposedly debilitating effects. Rawls' political conception of justice as fairness, for example, accomplishes this by resolving the question of political stability in the condition of plurality of comprehensive doctrines. The answer lies in what Rawls designates as reasonable and, as such, acceptable competing comprehensive doctrines. Reasonableness is achieved in two steps: first, by limiting comprehensive doctrines of the good life in the private realm and permitting only their aspects that can constitute the common conception of justice in the public; and second, by banning the unreasonable and sanctioning only the reasonable in society. In Rawls schema, the political conception of justice makes his theory of justice practical. In it, the overlapping consensus constituted from the common denominator among reasonable comprehensive doctrines is endorsed by citizens "as giving the content of their judgments on [political, social, and economic] institutions."³³ Meanwhile, Rawls accepts the fact that there will be unreasonable doctrines about the good life and suggests that they be contained so that they will not undermine the unity and stability of society. In a footnote, he asserts: "That there are doctrines that reject one or more democratic freedoms is itself a permanent fact of life, or seems so. This gives us the practical task of containing them—like war and disease—so that they do not overrun political justice."³⁴

In both Schmitt and Rawls, notwithstanding their endorsement of supposedly opposing forms of government, the political is the politics of the state. One way to understand the continuity of the concept of the political in these two disparate theories is to refer both to the kernel of state, whether absolute or liberal, power: the decision. Schmitt sees the decision as applied in the primary state task of deciding its friends and enemies. Meanwhile, in Rawls, the decision is displayed in the political recognition of the reasonable

²⁷ Badiou 2005b, 13-15, 143-145

²⁸ See Viroli, Maurizio. 1992. *From politics to reason of the state: The acquisition and transformation of the language of politics*, 1250-1600. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

²⁹ Schmitt 1996, 26

³⁰ Schmitt 1989, 65-78

³¹ Schmitt 1996, 37

³² Schmitt 1996, 46-47

³³ Rawls 1993, 11, 18, 29-35, 39

³⁴ Rawls 1993, 64:fn. 19

and in the elimination of the unreasonable. The logic in both instances is seen in consequence of the decision, and are the same: State power is the power to decide the exception: the protection of the law for friends and the reasonable, its suspension for enemies and the unreasonable. Giorgio Agamben³⁵ traces this logic from Hobbes' theory of the Sovereign. The power of the Sovereign is the power of the exception –the same power that each one of the multitude has in the state of nature, enabled by the capacities to judge and will, that is then given up through the covenant. What is given up by individuals, the covenant then designates as power that is solely that of the Sovereign's. Effectively then, the state of exception is the state of nature incarnated (within the commonwealth or as threshold in between) through the Sovereign decision.³⁶ To Agamben, the state of nature appears internal to the commonwealth and is manifested (among other appearances) as a state of dissolution. More specifically, it is the threshold that signal the foundation and the limit of the commonwealth: "The state of nature is, in truth, a state of exception, in which the city appears for an instant...*tanquam dissoluta*. The foundation is thus not an event achieved once and for all but is continually operative in the civil state in the form of the sovereign decision. What is more, the latter refers immediately to the life (and not the free will) of citizens, which thus appears as the originally political element, the *Urphanomen* of politics. Yet this life is not simply natural reproductive life, the *zoe* of the Greeks, nor *bios*, a qualified form of life. It is rather, the bare life of *homo sacer* and the *wargus*, a zone of indistinction and continuous transition between man and beast, nature and culture."³⁷

The Sovereign determines who or what is taken outside to this threshold, this zone of indistinction, where law is suspended and the power of the state is at its apex. The homo sacer is that which is taken out of law through the law's suspension. The homo sacer is analogous to Schmitt's enemy and Rawls' unreasonable, but more fundamentally, an animated body, life as such.

The state of exception has many names: state of emergency, **Martial Law**, state of lawlessness, etc.³⁸ But the logic is as Agamben claims: it is the suspension of the law to protect the lawful order –from calamities and disasters, from rebels or invaders, from the enemies of the state. We can think of the Marcos dictatorship and the present designation of the situation as a "state of lawlessness" as permanent states of exception. In both instances the state decides who is exempted or is taken out of the law and then acts accordingly. The act that comes from the decision can be perversely beneficial –the crony exempted from limitations on entrepreneurship put in place by law, the erring but socially/politically distinguished driver let go with a wave or salute by a traffic enforcer, the crooked cop reinstated so that he can continue to kill enemies of the state.³⁹ Or one can be at the receiving end of state violence –the Martial Law killed, tortured and disappeared, the OFW who lost his life trying to pass through a checkpoint,⁴⁰ the victims of extra-judicial killings. Here, we can unequivocally comprehend the point made by Walter Benjamin⁴¹ who, in his "Theses on the philosophy of history" asserts, "[T]he 'state of emergency' in which we live is not the exception but the rule."⁴²

But Badiou himself mostly directs his criticism of the political versus Arendt in the matter of truth and opinion. In particular, he argues against the idea that politics is the "public exercise of judgment" or that it concerns only the interests of public opinion: "As soon as 'politics' finds its sole rightful place in public opinion it goes without saying that the theme of truth is excluded from it."⁴³ Indeed, Arendt argues for the exclusion of philosophical truth, the kind of truth that preoccupied philosophy since Plato, in political or public affairs. She claims, quite compellingly, that the weight of such truth will stifle debate. But

³⁶ Agamben 1998, 35-37 & 105-109

³⁷ Agamben 1998, 109

³⁸ Agamben, Giorgio. 2005. *State of Exception*. Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 4

³⁹ GMA News Online. 2017. "Supt. Marcos reinstated, named CIDG-SOCCSKSARGEN chief." *GMA News*. July 13.

Accessed July 13, 2017. <http://www.gmanetwork.com/news/news/nation/617899/supt-marcos-reinstated-named-nbsp-cidg-soccsksargen-chief/story>

⁴⁰ Amoroso, Ed. 2016. "4 cops sacked over OFW's slay." *Philippine Star*. September 26. Accessed December 10, 2016.

<http://www.philstar.com/nation/2016/09/26/1627294/4-cops-sacked-over-ofws-slay>

⁴¹ Benjamin, Walter. 1968. "Theses on the philosophy of history," in *Illuminations: Essays and reflections*. Edited by Hannah Arendt. New York: Schocken Books

⁴² Benjamin 1968, 257

⁴³ Badiou 2005, 13

short, the elite rule the country.

The obvious question is "Why then are the ruling ideas – or the fantasy– not the ideas/fantasy of the elite?" Zizek explains that the "ruling ideology, in order to be operative, has to incorporate a series of features in which the exploited/dominated majority will be able to recognize its authentic longings... [in addition to] its 'distortion' by the relations of domination and exploitation."¹⁰⁴ This begs the question "Why not the fantasy of the masses?" Tolentino explains. "*ang gitnang uring fantasya ang epektibo at makapangyarihang ethos at etika [bilang pagpupursige] ng paggagap sa kolektibong pagdanas sa kasalatan.*" Further, "[h]inihikayat ng estado ang mga negosyo na patagusin ang gitnang uring panuntunan pati sa nagdarahap."¹⁰⁵ As such, the middle class experience is available to the poor as *load na barya barya, kosmetinong naka-sachet, inisnatch na cellphone at alahas, sinikwat na damit pamporma*. Middle class fantasy as middle class experience is the aspiration of the poor, "*lente ng pagdanas ng kasapatan,*" "[*patunay*] na mayroon pang mas magandang buhay lampas [sa materyal na kahirapan]."¹⁰⁶

Thus, even though the middle class position is itself precarious as it is always in danger of backsliding into poverty, it is still a very much-desired position. Additionally, for Tolentino, the middle class experience is also unsustainable, erratic, and as such unsatisfying. It is at most a waiting for a promised future: a stable and adequate income in a developed economy, a better government that responds to our needs, a society that secures our properties and is just. This waiting is melancholic.¹⁰⁷ But for the poor majority, there is no beyond: "*Ang rekurso ng abang mamamayan ay manalig na rin sa gitnang uring fantasya –ito o ano pa? Wala nang lampas pa rito.*"¹⁰⁸ Also, in the actual experience of the fantasy as the consumption of popular culture in the context of global neoliberal capitalism, "[*may*] katambal na kasiyahan na nadanas sa kultural na karanasan."¹⁰⁹

Tolentino's objective in his cultural critique of the primarily economic middle class fantasy is how to make it political. More specifically, "...*paano sisimulan ang kontraryong fantasy-production para sa aktuwal na pagbabalikwas?*"¹¹⁰ He does not claim that middle class fantasy is not entirely without politics. He argues that the middle class has appropriated the domain of civil society and as such it incorporates within its fantasy the perks of a civilized living together –from liberal democracy to people power to civil rights. However, he asserts that these have become ineffective, that the middle class is experiencing "People Power fatigue."¹¹¹

But this is precisely the weakness in Tolentino's critique. He fails to recognize that *gitnang uring pantasya* is political before it is economic or cultural. Its origin is the event of EDSA. If the middle class cannot muster the numbers to make a new people power, it is because it does not have that power in the first place. But it imagines that it had the power before and that power is lost. As such, the middle class is the substitute empty signifier for the sublime that was the people of EDSA. And ultimately, the middle class fantasy is, at the most fundamental, a fantasy of lost agency.

It is obvious that Tolentino is indebted to Zizek/Lacan, from the concepts of fantasy ("*fantasya*") to enjoyment ("*kasiyahan*") that he deploys without attribution. As such he is unfettered from engaging the philosophical foundations of these concepts. But this also why it is easy for him to fall prey to the standard or commonplace response to the problem of ideology that belies the potential complexity of his critique: "*Politikal na pagkilos ang katugunan –sa antas ng indibidwal, ang pagtaas ng kamulatan, at pag-ugnay nitong mataas na kamulatan sa kilusang masa tungo sa mobilisasyon at organisasyon.*"¹¹² He also, thus, fails to recognize that his political position is well within the scope of the middle class fantasy that he criticizes.

The doubled political middle class post-EDSA politics

The power of the middle class is its fantasy. It doesn't have the numbers, unlike the poor majority. It doesn't have direct access to the powers of the state, unlike the elite. But its fantasy expressed in

¹⁰³ Anderson 1995, 28-29

¹⁰⁴ Zizek 1999, 185

¹⁰⁵ Tolentino 2010, x and xi

¹⁰⁶ Tolentino 2010, xxiv and xxix

¹⁰⁷ Tolentino 2010, xxii-xxiv

¹⁰⁸ Tolentino 2010, xxx

¹⁰⁹ Tolentino 2010, xxxiv

¹¹⁰ Tolentino 2010, x

¹¹¹ Tolentino 2010, xxxi

¹¹² Tolentino 2010, xxxviii

But first, we must account for the *masa* of EDSA 3. It was not the third EDSA⁹⁴ that made the split of the mass from the people of the first EDSA unequivocal, but the electoral cheating and subsequent death of the presidential candidate and would-be *masa* redeemer Fernando Poe Jr. (FPJ). We know that through his movies, the masses saw FPJ as their savior. Nick Joaquin⁹⁵ recognized this as early as 1968, “Poe is a fairytale hero, embodying the pitiful populist dreams of salvation that get translated mythically, into a Bernardo Carpio or, politically, into a Magsaysay... if he lacks the Nowness of...Zaldy [Zsornack] or... Estrada, it's because he feeds an older hunger in the masses.” Soledad Reyes points out⁹⁶ that “[o]f his generation who emerged in the 1950's, only Fernando Poe Jr. continued to appear in films for almost fifty years.”⁹⁷ Just as the masses were taught to read and listen within the traditions and conventions of popular culture for centuries as Reyes asserts, the masses watched FPJ's films repeatedly for decades. The continuity in motifs, themes and narrative strategy between popular culture and FPJ movies made possible the popular appropriation of his films as *salamin ng buhay* – “as a reading of recalcitrant reality itself.”⁹⁸ This means that if FPJ is the masses' messiah, the oppressed life portrayed and that he redeems in his movies are their lives. In the mass consumption of FPJ's movies, contextualized by their history and their culture,⁹⁹ FPJ's persona and narrative are already translated and appropriated notionally by the mass. They are ready to be constituents of a subjectivity that can then be enacted. The 2004 elections, itself, was the mechanism that transformed FPJ's mass appeal into mass support. It paved the way for the specter, that sinister¹⁰⁰ subjectivity that was the mass vote. To an extent the FPJ campaign recognized the process that was unfolding as he enjoined the Filipino mass, “*Sama-sama nating pandayin and ating kinabukasan!*” What, in effect, the FPJ campaign was doing was offering his messianic movie persona and the myth associated with it for enactment by the Filipino mass. FPJ is the last Pinoy messiah. His death in December of 2004 signaled for the masses a political passing: their political salvation is no longer possible. And thus the mass disappeared as re-presentation in the political.

And the traditional elite? According to Benedict Anderson,¹⁰¹ the period following the reconstruction after World War II until the declaration of Martial Law in 1972 was the heyday of what he calls as Philippine *cacique* democracy. The political dynasties of today were established and then consolidated. Guns, goons and gold decided political elections. Local governments become bailiwicks that ensured positions of influence and power in national politics, especially in Congress. But the Filipino elite were then outmaneuvered and outgunned by Marcos who turned out to be the biggest *cacique* of all. The whole country became his bailiwick, with the help of the military and bankrolled by the wealth that he confiscated from the oligarchs and that he plundered from the nation's coffers.¹⁰²

Cory Aquino's revolutionary government that came into power immediately after the EDSA revolution was the site of struggle between the multitudes of social forces that participated in the people power revolution. From the side of the traditional elite that was marginalized during the dictatorship, there was a big push for national and local elections. National elections were held in May 1987 for twenty-four senatorial and 200 congressional seats. The results were exceptionally agreeable for them as they once again dominate Congress. The local election held early the next year (in January 1988) led to the “fuller revival of the ancient regime” as the traditional politicians overwhelming took control of former bailiwicks.¹⁰³ In

⁹³ Tolentino 2010, x-xii

⁹⁴ This EDSA revolt has been, for the most part, ignored by political analysis as it was ignored by the mainstream media when it happened. The middle class forces that made up EDSA Dos begrudge the opposed uprising the dignity of the EDSA appellation.

⁹⁵ Joaquin, Nick 1968. “Batang Taquilla.” *Philippine Free Press*. Accessed December 10, 2016. <http://www.fpj-daking.blogspot.com/2008/09/fpj-batang-taquilla-by-quijano-de-manila.html>

⁹⁶ Reyes, Soledad 2009. *Dama to Szasa Zatumah: Desire and Fantasy*. Pasig City: Anvil Publishing

⁹⁷ Reyes 2009, 102

⁹⁸ Reyes 2009, 121

⁹⁹ See Iletto, Reynaldo 1998. *Pasyon and Revolution: Popular Movements in the Philippines, 1840-1910*. Quezon City: Ateneo De Manila University Press

¹⁰⁰ For the middle class, at least.

¹⁰¹ Anderson, Benedict. 1995. “Cacique democracy in the Philippines: Origins and dreams.” *Discrepant histories: Translocal essays on Filipino culture*. Edited by Vicente Rafael. Philadelphia: Temple University Press

¹⁰² Anderson 1995, 21-23

Arendt and her politics can live with facts. For Arendt, facts cannot decide political concerns but can only assist judgments towards consensus. The form that fact-informed judgments in politics take is that of opinions, and debate is seen to sort out the superior ones. But beyond this are more important political effects: debate accommodates the plural condition of politics, it enables the “appearance” of individuals who are schooled and who train and sharpen their judgments in their engagement with others, and this politics of public engagement makes community.⁴⁴

The conflict between Badiou's truth and Arendt's judgment or opinion here underlies differences in their conception of politics. Badiou faults Arendt's version of politics precisely as a limiting of politics to the political or to state politics. Indeed, while Arendt privileges “nascence” and the creation of the new in her political philosophy and while she praises the creative power of revolutions to clear the way for a beginning,⁴⁶ she does not provide the mechanism or identify the process in which opinions in debate can lead to revolution, or to any event or subjectivity that can create the new. For Badiou then, such plurality of opinions is simply the plurality of parties in a parliamentary arrangement. And voting, its preferred procedure to resolve differences is “foreign to all truth,”⁴⁷ so that for those who support this vision of politics philosophically, “it is necessary to sever ‘the political from the protocols of decision, to reduce it to the judgment of the spectator, and to think of debate as a plural confrontation of opinions without truth.’”⁴⁸

But how does *truth* relate to politics? And are Badiou and Arendt speaking of the same truth? First they agree that truths are not facts. But Badiou goes further and also distinguishes between truth and knowledge. Badiou states, “As long as nothing happens, aside from that which conforms to the rules of a state of things, there can admittedly be cognition, correct statements, accumulated knowledge; there cannot be truth.”⁴⁹ What truth indicates is beyond whatever we can claim about the *situation* or state of things. Truth traverses and changes the situation. This puts Badiou in opposition to Foucault as well. For Foucault, knowledge or the discourse of truth is intimately linked to the relations of power and the arrangement of its institutions and structures. In Foucault's schema, as in Arendt, knowledge can be deployed politically. But beyond Arendt, Foucault recognizes that the power of knowledge is its truth. In Foucault, one cannot really uncouple them (as Arendt requires) as the production and reproduction of any state of affairs depend on how they buttress both the configuration and application of power.⁵⁰ For Foucault, truth/knowledge is ideology. Needless to say, this is not Badiou's truth either. For Badiou, truth creates “a hole in knowledge.”⁵¹

In Badiou's philosophy, truth, event, politics, and philosophy are related concepts. *Truth* is not philosophical truth in the sense that it is produced by philosophy. He notes that no philosophical statement can be said to be meaningfully true. But truth can be produced through the generic procedures that condition philosophy: science, art/literature, love, and politics. These conditions are truth procedures that unfold the truth that can only be after, and of, an *event*. Truth, here, is a paradox: “it is at once something new, hence something rare and exceptional, yet, touching the being of that which it is a truth, it is also the most stable, the closest, ontologically speaking, to the initial state of things.”⁵² The *event* is the interruption of a situation or state of things. It appears out of nowhere in the sense that the situation does not see it coming. The resources of the situation cannot understand it or even name it and, as such, it is radical. It erupts from the impossible, and thus unrepresented, parts of the situation and, as such, is traumatic and atypical. It is a supplement to the situation that allows the deployment of a truth procedure relative to the

⁴⁴ Arendt 1968, 310-312

⁴⁵ Following Immanuel Kant, Arendt privileges the role of judgment in politics. In fact, she reconstructs Kant's political philosophy on the basis of his third *Critique*. But Arendt appears to err in linking and likening judgment to opinion. See her *Lectures on Kant's Political Philosophy* where, for example, she says, “Maxims apply and are needed only for matters of opinion and judgments” (Arendt 1992, Twelfth Session). Further, in a debate with Jurgen Habermas, she insists that truth has no role in political judgments, the scope of which is properly the space of opinions (See Beiner 1992, 136-37). Meanwhile, a simple word search of Kant's book finds no more than twenty instances of the word opinion. There are only four occurrences in the “Critique of the Aesthetic Power of Judgment” where Kant uses the word in the ordinary way and does not seem to deploy it conceptually. There are sixteen occurrences of opinion in the “Critique of the Teleological Power of Judgment” but Kant does not in any way treat the word as interchangeable with judgment (see for example Kant, Immanuel. 2000. *Critique of the Power of Judgment*. Edited by Paul Guyer, translated by Paul Guyer and Eric Matthews. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, Sections 90 [5:461 and 465] and 91 [5:467]).

⁴⁶ See Arendt, Hannah. 1963. *On Revolution*. New York: The Viking Press

⁴⁷ “[I]t brings Hitler to power just as easily as Pétain or the Algerian Islamists.” (Badiou 2005b, 16)

⁴⁸ Badiou 2005b, 16, 24

⁴⁹ Badiou 1999, 36

⁵⁰ Foucault, Michel. 1980. *Power/Knowledge*. Edited by C. Gordon. New York: Harvester, 92-108

⁵¹ Badiou 1999, 36

⁵² Badiou 1999, 36

state of things. Badiou, for example, describes the May 1968 student and worker uprising in France this way: “[The participants were] seized by what was happening to them, as if by something extraordinary, something properly incalculable . . . well beyond what any one person might have thought possible –that’s what I call an evental dimension. None of the little processes that led to the event was equal to what actually took place . . . I simply think that none of the calculations internal to the situation can account for its interruption, and cannot, in particular, elucidate this kind of break in scale that happens at a certain moment, such that the actors themselves are seized by something of which they no longer know if they are its actors or its vehicle [supports], or what carries it away.”⁵³ To the participants of this event, by virtue of being its subject, the event itself demands that they, through their politics, produce its truth.

The generation of truths from a political event is the task of *a politics*. First, Badiou says that an event belongs to politics when its material is collective or if it can only be qualified in relation to a “collective multiplicity.” Collective, here, “means immediately universalizing” in the sense that the thought that comes with the event “belongs to all.” This thought identifies a subject of the event and constitutes such as a militant of the truth procedure. The acts of militants/subjects, if they are in fidelity with the event, produce the truths of the event. This is Badiou’s politics: the seizing and being seized by an event, and the generation of its truths.⁵⁴ Second, this politics “presents as such the infinite character of situations.” This infinity is the boundless possibility of any situation that is obscured by the excess of the *state of the situation*.⁵⁵ The deliberation about the possible constitutes the process of politics. And politics “treats infinity as such according to the principle of the same, the egalitarian principle.”⁵⁶ Third, politics summons the excess that is the power of the state. To Badiou, this power is errant or unmeasured. But politics is answered by “a show of power by the State” in the form of repression, which then reveals the inadequacy of the state to the situation and to the event. Politics “fixes the power of the State,” it configures it, it measures it: “Freedom here consists in putting the State at a distance through the collective establishment of a measure. . . [a]nd if [it] can be measured, it is because the collective can measure up to it.”⁵⁷

Tinimbang ka ngunit kulang! Or more specifically: *Tinimbang ng EDSA people power ang diktadurya at nabuko ang taglay nitong kakulangan*. Indeed, EDSA was an event. But the concept of “*kakulangan*” here is not really an adequate stand in for what Badiou wants to demonstrate. His preferred measure is that of distance, which then introduces a space wherein politics can be pursued freely and away from the state. But “lack” is suitable in a different mode of demonstrating Badiou that is not strictly Badiou. It points towards the *subject*, which was also EDSA. Nevertheless, EDSA was a measuring. Before the uprising, the power of the dictatorship was measureless. Earlier attempts by a politics that traces its lineage to the First Quarter Storm⁵⁸ that stunned the Marcos regime prior to the declaration of Martial Law have only encountered a power that is greater and immense. EDSA was different:

EDSA, February 1986. People Power, an uprising. It is also remembered as a “peaceful revolution.” That is when millions of Filipinos overwhelmed a ten-lane avenue that is crammed between two military camps that headquartered the Army and the then Philippine Constabulary. They also overwhelmed armored vehicles and soldiers in battle gear, 20 years of state terror, kidnappings and disappearances, murder, then martial rule, 20 years of fear. The uprising was solemn, as military maneuvers were confronted with entwined arms and prayers. It was festive, as fear was driven away with singing, as the bursting noise of gunfire was forestalled and silenced with flowers inserted in the barrels of automatic rifles. It was uniting, as individuals bordered by skin but otherwise undifferentiated became a mass of chanting, grim and then smiling faces, directed anger, strong and unshakable resolve, undulating wall of worldly flesh impervious to tanks, granite-hard will, a people.

The sheer number of people that eventually took the initiative away from the plotters overtook what was at first a coup against the Marcos dictatorship that was designed to ride on the wave of protests that has engulfed Manila’s streets.

The people stayed in EDSA for four days and would have stayed longer had not the dictator fled. Then

⁵³ Quoted in Hewlett, Nick. 2010. Badiou, Balibar, Ranciere: Re-thinking Emancipation. London: Continuum, 39

⁵⁴ Badiou 2005b, 141-142

⁵⁵ The state of the situation is the state or the political that re-presents all the possible combinations of the things present in a situation in manners that excessive to the infinity of the situation. What politics calls forth is the infinity of the situation itself, of the incompatible multiplicity that constitutes it. See also Badiou, Alain. 2005a. *Being and Event*. Translated by Oliver Feltham.

⁵⁶ London: Continuum

⁵⁷ Badiou 2005b, 142-143

⁵⁸ Badiou 2005b, 143-145

⁵⁹ See Lacaba, Jose. 1982. *Days of Disquiet, nights of Rage: The First Quarter Storm and Other Related Events*. Manila: Salinlahi Publications and Santos, Soliman and Santos, Paz. Eds. 2008. *Militant but groovy: Stories of Samahang Demokratikong Kabataan*. Manila: Anvil

is agonizing so we fill in ourselves through the Other, mainly experienced as an authority who knows us for us.⁸⁷

The workings of *ideology*, according to Althusser, are precisely a second-degree relation of our imaginary relations: “Ideology is a ‘representation’ of the imaginary relationship of individuals to their real conditions of existence.”⁸⁸ In this sense it is more complicated than Marx’s false consciousness, more complex than the assertion that ideology are ruling ideas of the dominant class. For Žizek, Lacan’s formula for fantasy, already laid out above, is most appropriate. Our inaccessibility to ourselves as subjects is filled by the *imaginary*, by a version of us as objects in the social world: ego, individual, citizen, class, people, nation, the state. But, of course, we can only know ourselves as such through the Other, through the organizing power that designates us precisely as such, through the institutions, rituals, and norms that we perform in order to identify and accept ourselves as such. In Žizek, the many designations for our supposed objective selves are also the master signifiers of a political order. These signifiers are ultimately empty in that they really do not designate anything real but are instead containers for meaningfulness. They are what he also calls as the “sublime objects of ideology.”⁸⁹ They function precisely to re-signify the subject, and as such, the subject’s beliefs about itself, into the *Symbolic* order. Thus there is no people as such but we do designate ourselves as a people. There is no nation as such but we do believe ourselves to be the nation. We have no direct knowledge, of “people” and “nation” but we believe others do, or the State does.

Fantasy is a way in which ideology works. Within the register of the *Imaginary*, it is the invented scenario “occupying the place of the *Real*.”⁹⁰ In a way, it functions like Marx’s concept of reification: We focus on the supposed object itself; the new immaculately packaged smartphone, for example, gives us the experience of unwrapping it as if it exists just for us, as if it has no existence before we revealed it from its wrappings. This belies or erases the real social relations that produced it –the underpaid and overworked factory worker, the dangerous working conditions, the factory accidents, and the incidents of worker suicides.⁹¹ But fantasy is more complicated; it works precisely by deploying itself as a modality of Lacan’s (and Žizek’s) triad of registers –the Real-Imaginary-Symbolic.⁹² To Lacan, the imaginary-symbolic registers comprise our reality. The real, meanwhile, is something that the symbolic fails to represent or signify: the subject as such, the real relations of exploitation as such, freedom, the Thing(-in-itself), the new. . . Fantasy works, like the empty signifiers, to re/signify us into the symbolic order. But it also gives us a sampling, a foretaste of the real in place of the real –to that impossible subjectivity that is our truth.

Gitnang-uring pantasya

The object-ego of our post-EDSA ideology is, of course, the middle class. And the fantasy is indeed thoroughly middle-class. Rolando Tolentino calls it *gitnang uring pantasya*. There are many ways to understand middle class fantasy: the middle class itself as a societal category is fantasy, middle class life-experience is fantasy, and the fantasy that rationalizes and structure society originates from the middle class. Tolentino emphasizes all three at the nexus between the economy and popular culture: consumerism within global capitalism and its neoliberal rationality. This consumerism is a measure for what can be considered middle class, it is the expression of actual middle class experience promised and anticipated as a possible future, and it is how the middle class reproduces itself and the societal status quo.⁹³

⁸⁷ Žizek, Slavoj. 1991. *For they know not what they do: Enjoyment as a political factor*, New York: Verso, 61-72

⁸⁸ Eagleton, Terry. 1994. *Ideology*. London: Longman, 89 and 101

⁸⁹ Žizek 1991, xx and I

⁹⁰ Žizek 1991, xii

⁹¹ See the New York Times’ series on Apple and Foxconn. The series won a Pulitzer Prize for explanatory reporting on April 15, 2013. NYT. 2012. *Economy*. *New York Times*. Accessed December 18, 2016. http://www.nytimes.com/interactive/business/economy.html?_r=0

⁹² “There are three modalities of the Real: the ‘real Real’ (the horrifying Thing, the primordial object, from Irma’s throat to the Alien); the ‘symbolic Real’ (the real as consistency: the signifier reduced to a senseless formula, like quantum physics formulas which can no longer be translated back into -or related to -the everyday experience of our life-world); and the ‘imaginary Real’ (the mysterious *je ne sais quoi*, the unfathomable ‘something’ on account of which the sublime dimension shines through an ordinary object). The Real is thus, in effect, all three dimensions at the same time: the abyssal vortex which ruins every consistent structure; the mathematized consistent structure of reality; the fragile pure appearance. And, in a strictly homologous way, there are three modalities of the Symbolic (the real -the signifier reduced to a senseless formula; the imaginary -the Jungian ‘symbols’; and the symbolic -speech, meaningful language); and three modalities of the Imaginary (the real -fantasy, which is precisely an imaginary scenario occupying the place of the Real; the imaginary - image as such in its fundamental function of a decoy; and the symbolic -again, the Jungian ‘symbols’ or New Age archetypes). In Žizek 1991, xii

Correspondingly, *sa ating lupang hinirang*, the subject of the first EDSA is misrecognized as the middle class of EDSA 2, or as the mass of EDSA 3, or, in the case of the fundamental time-travelling post-hoc misrecognition within the political fantasy, as the middle class that was EDSA 1. EDSA is split in the theoretical sense of being barred from itself, but also in the sense of being reduced to its parts that are not adequate even when conceived as whole, whose putative unity and agency is forever lost –and now available only as fantasy. But what is this fantasy?

The fantasy object of EDSA' void is middle class agency

In an earlier paper,⁷⁹ I tried to present two stories of politics through Hobbes and Hegel. I argued that the Hobbesian story of humanity's movement from the state of nature to the Commonwealth is a story of political alienation, a reversed Hegelian history that tells how we leave politics behind (in the state of nature) in order to pursue animal or mere life (in the Aristotelian sense of *zoe*, a life devoted to the satisfaction of needs) under the absolute rule of the Sovereign. Hegel's story of humanity's movement towards self-consciousness is held as an ideal. Of course, this is not really achieved in Hegel, an opening that eventually Marx filled with his theory of proletarian revolt. So much of Marxist theorizing after Marx has been devoted to why this revolt never came to be or became the totalitarian monster we know from history. Meanwhile, in Hegel's world, we are the unhappy consciousness, futilely trying to fill the void of who we are with what Hegel describes as the many variations of reasonableness⁸⁰ and spirituality.⁸¹ In Zizek, through Hegel and Lacan, these two trajectories coincide in the problem of ideology.

The fate of the unhappy consciousness in Hegel is of particular relevance to the concept of ideology. In the unfolding of Hegel's history, the subject stoically withdraws into the impotent protection of abstract reason and virtue that it reveals to be as empty, or sceptically withdraws into a theoretical and practical wariness that is also emptiness. The extreme pathological form of spiritual withdrawal available to the subject is when consciousness, incapable of extricating itself from the irrationality of things, simply identifies itself with such, and then externalizes its true form of rational universality into the impossible beyond.⁸² To Lacan,⁸³ this is basically the effect of the subject of the unconscious, always unspecified, misrecognizing itself as the object, and as such knowable, ego. Or as the subject of enunciation, always unsayable, misrecognizing itself as the predicable subject of the enunciated.⁸⁴

This process is also traceable in the child's (between 6 and 18 months) great pleasure in her mirror image. According to Lacan, the image promises the unified and adept individual self that the child then anticipates, this is despite the child's experience of the fragmented body "still trapped in his motor impotence and nursing dependence."⁸⁵ Part of the of the recognition is attributable to the child's parents identifying him in his mirror image, or urging and cheering her on as she does so. The point here is that the self is experienced as something external, an image-thing embedded in the child's relation with others. For Lacan, the self is not the result of an organic and innate development but is decentered, external, and invested in something other (in the image-thing and in the dynamics of the child's relation with her parents). The child's desire also gets decentered in a correlative process wherein needs turn to demands for the parent's recognition and love.⁸⁶ The mirror-image is thus tied to what becomes the "social I" and the "desire through the other" learned and constituted precisely by how the social puts us into place and how we demand and accept such place and placement.

Zizek deploys these concepts politically, and we can follow the argument from a reinterpretation of Lacan's mirror stage. Zizek says that this metaphor of the mirror shows how as adults, ideology structures our relations with others and with the Other. I look at myself in the mirror and I know that the image I see is not the real "I". There is something that the image lacks. This may be experienced as anxiety over the persistent question that we ask ourselves: "Who/what am I?" I need others to fill in this lack, this void. I need an other to recognize me. This other must know what is lacking. Thus, the question then becomes "What does the other want from me?" Whatever the other wants is what I am. This other is our mother, then our father, then the church, the nation, the state, etc. The point is: our experience of ourselves as a lack

⁷⁹ See Malabed, Rizalino. 2012. "Leaving Politics Behind: Arendt and Hegelian Reading of Hobbes," *Philosophia: International Journal of Philosophy*, 41(1): 83-98

⁸⁰ Hegel 1977, §§231-437

⁸¹ Hegel 1977, §§488-526

⁸² Hegel 1977, §§197-229

⁸³ Lacan, Jacques. 2006. *Écrits*. New York: W.W. Norton

⁸⁴ Lacan 2006, 757-758; Zizek 1993, 14

⁸⁵ Lacan 2006, 76

⁸⁶ Lacan 2006, 75-81

the overwhelming crowd poured into the other streets of the capital. Mendiola Bridge, permanently transformed into a barrier by the military and police to protect Philippine presidents from the people's anger, was occupied. And beyond it, Malacanang Palace was besieged, inundated, claimed.

The subject of EDSA is the night of the world

What is a truth of EDSA? *People* is power. The *people* that materialized in EDSA was all the individuals: poor, middle-class and rich, families, crowds, organizations and unions, alliances, factions, icons, rosaries and flowers, held photographs of the killed and disappeared, smiles and embraces, resolve, all the others that poured into different avenues and streets in other cities. But the people of power that was EDSA was more than these elements and parts put together. It was not an aggregation, not critical mass, but the singular *subject* of the event⁵⁹ which was also universal as it beckoned to all. Beyond those who watched their TVs, beyond those who listened to radios, beyond those who speak our various languages and reside in these islands... it called to all the possibilities of the multiplicity that is all of the world: This momentary, singular but universal, people can alter the world, empty it of meaning, explode its structures into fragments, and inscribe within this void limitless possibilities. People is action.

Within the political, what is people? It is the populace; it is split into the many but placed and determined, named and counted. It also the undifferentiated mass of everyone but not really, summoned in name only in every political speech, useful as pretext for every political act. It is ultimately an empty sign, we cannot point to it in the world, we cannot recognize it, we cannot define it without contradiction. In the political, people is subjection.

The people that was EDSA is an impossible subjectivity of immense power on the verge of creating a new world.

However, the possibility of forming a new government for the same state (whose authoritarian facade receded when the dictator fled) was within the range of possible effects of EDSA. This was actualized and things quickly went back to the comfortable familiarity of the political.

The new Aquino government hastily yielded to American demands and reneged on its promise to remove the US bases from Philippine soil. Rolando Olalia, a popular labor leader, and his driver were abducted and found tortured and murdered in late 1986. Thirteen farmers were slaughtered at the Mendiola Bridge in a January 1987 mobilization by peasant organizations demanding land reform. Within the same month, two individuals were killed and twelve were wounded when police again fired at a rally protesting the Mendiola massacre. In September 1987, Lean Alejandro, a former student leader and secretary-general of the radical *Bagong Alyansang Makabayan*, was assassinated with a shotgun that blew away half of his face. Rebel soldiers made several coup attempts that transformed Manila streets into battlegrounds in 1987 and 1989. Military sponsored vigilante groups were on a rampage of mutilation, torture, and massacre in the countryside causing widespread fear among rural folks.⁶⁰

Nonetheless, the rhetoric of the Aquino government was similar to those who rose to protest it –being borne out of the same anti-dictatorship campaign. Besides, the press was freed, a new democratic Constitution was ratified, and elections were held. More importantly, the government took over the commemoration of the uprising that ended the dictatorship and converted it into an annual spectacle of speeches, Catholic mass, and performances by popular actors and performers. And the people who attended the celebrations or watched the broadcasts inaugurated their transformation into ordinary spectators. And EDSA, itself, was on its way to becoming history and nostalgia.

But not before two more uprisings, which are qualitatively different from the first, erupted into the political scene. The 2001 EDSAs can be seen as protests by parts of the original and are markers of its split. EDSA 2 was an uprising by the middle class. EDSA 3 was the inaugurating protest of the *masa*.

Contrary to the momentary singularity and universality of the subject of the event, or more precisely, after the event of such an absolute subjectivity, the subject to Slavoj Zizek⁶¹, is split and is only quieted by

⁵⁹ This is actually going beyond Badiou, as the subject of the event for him is the militant that acts in fidelity to but after the event. In this metapolitics, I equivocate between the subject of the event, which is the same as claiming that the event was self-aware during its duration', and the militant of the event, whose politics is the production of its truth.

⁶⁰ For a recounting of the experiences following the EDSA revolution and the establishment of a new government, see Appendix I of Davis, Leonard. 1989. *Revolutionary Struggle in the Philippines*. New York: St. Martin's Press

⁶¹ Zizek, Slavoj. 1993. *Tarrying with the negative: Kant, Hegel, and the critique of ideology*. Durham: Duke University Press

its misrecognized self. Or, to offer a foretaste of Zizek's method: "How can it not know what it is?"—this is Deckard (Harrison Ford) confronted and bewildered by the enigma of the replicant Rachael's (Sean Young) self-identification as a human in Ridley Scott's *Blade Runner*.⁶² Of course, following Deckard's perplexity, the relevant question for us post-EDSA is: "How can we not know who we are?" This asking seems to require that we are somehow alert about being deceived. And the question is a renunciation of who we think we are and is a step towards self-discovery? Is self-knowledge even possible? Or, in asking the question, do we think ourselves exempt from its implications, wherein the use of "we" is meant to condescend? Deckard's situation in this part of the movie's unfolding is ironic in that he himself identifies as human and is unaware of his nature as a machine. We can thus echo Deckard: How can he not know what he is? But a more pressing but not necessarily prior question is: If he does not know what he is, is he self-conscious—a subjectivity? To Zizek, the problem of the deceived replicant is the problem of the subject of our time: "Today... our perception of reality, including the reality of our innermost self-experience, depends upon symbolic fictions."⁶³ At the end of the movie, after reacquiring full memory, Deckard himself confronts the question as applied to himself and he is straightaway deprived of his self-identity. Contrary to the common notion that recollection reconnects us to our lost selves, "... in the universe of *Blade Runner*... recollection designates something incomparably more radical: the total loss of the hero's symbolic identity."⁶⁴

Thus, to ask the question "How can we not know who we are?" in our current post-EDSA dystopian reality is not to prod ourselves towards self-identity but to push ourselves towards the insight that we are not who we think we are, that "who we are" is our all too reasonable enslaving fiction. And if pushed further: there is no longer a "we," no "us," only silence that is not sign, an empty space where and when we should be, a "night in the world."⁶⁵ The problem, of course, is that we are not really asking this question yet with the unbearable fear and the irreverent audacity that it deserves. And our reality, as such, remains safe from us.

The relevant concept here is the *subject*. And for Zizek, the appropriate starting point is "the spectre that is haunting Western academia" and that is uniting the diverse philosophical positions of the new age obscurantist and the postmodern deconstructionist, the Habermasian and the Heideggerian, the cognitive scientist and the deep ecologist, and the critical (post-)Marxist and feminist into an opposition: the Cartesian subject.⁶⁶ Of course it is Zizek himself who summons this spectre as the starting point of his critique of ideology. But after holding up this apparition he immediately offers a disclaimer: "The point, of course, is not to return to the *cogito* in the guise in which this notion has dominated modern thought (the self-transparent thinking subject), but to bring to light its forgotten obverse, the excessive, unacknowledged kernel of the *cogito*, which is far from the pacifying image of the transparent Self."⁶⁷

What Rene Descartes' "I think" does upon its enunciation is to "introduce a crack in the ontologically consistent universe," so much so that the ghostly presence who, "behind my back, dominates me and pulls the strings of what I experience as 'reality'" becomes notionally manifest. But *cogito* here falls short of its potential as "correlative to the whole of reality"⁶⁸—"the autonomous agent which 'spontaneously' constitutes the objective world opposed to itself." This is because it is reduced to *res cogitans* and, as such, becomes mere representation of a deficient being that calls forth, necessarily, the superior representation of a perfect being that in turn guarantees the whole lot of our representations of the world, and as such, the world. The *cogito*, then, becomes merely "one among many representations in an intricate totality, part of reality and not yet (or, in Hegelese, only 'in itself') correlative to the whole of reality."⁶⁹

⁶² Zizek 1993, 15. A sequel, *Blade Runner 2049*, was recently released to general critical acclaim and disappointing commercial performance. A review by Zizek raises questions of dystopic post-human capitalism and self-consciousness characterized by the recognition and appreciation of counterfactuals. See Zizek, Slavoj. 2017. "Blade Runner 2049: A view of post-human capitalism." *The Philosophical Salon*. Accessed October 30, 2017. <http://www.thephilosophicalsalon.com/blade-runner-2049-a-view-of-post-human-capitalism/>

⁶³ Zizek 1993, 11

⁶⁴ Zizek 1993, 11

⁶⁵ Zizek attributes the phrase to GWF Hegel who uses it to designate the void that is the subject. See Zizek, Slavoj. 1999. *The Ticklish Subject: The absent center of political ontology*. London: Verso, 2. See also Hegel, GWF. 1977. *Phenomenology of the spirit*. Translated by AV Miller, Oxford: Oxford University Press

⁶⁶ Zizek 1999, 1

⁶⁷ Zizek 1999, 2

⁶⁸ "...i.e., as the point external to reality, exempted from it, which delineates reality's horizon (in the sense of Wittgenstein's well known *Tractatus* metaphor on the eye that can never be part of the seen reality)." (Zizek 1993, 13)

⁶⁹ Zizek 1993, 12-13

But Kant comes to the rescue and "fully articulates the inherent paradoxes of self-consciousness... [what his] 'transcendental turn' renders manifest is the impossibility of locating the subject in the 'great chain of being,' into the Whole of the universe—all those notions of the universe as a harmonious Whole in which every element has its own place."⁷⁰ What Descartes gets wrong is the supposed spontaneous self-presentation and self-understanding of the thing that thinks in the utterance of *cogito* or in the moment of self-consciousness. For Zizek, Kant's critique calls attention to the "topological discord between the form 'I think' and the substance which thinks, i.e., the distinction between the analytical proposition on the identity of the logical subject of thought, contained in 'I think,' and the synthetical proposition on the identity of a person qua thinking thing-substance."⁷¹ Thus the answer, finally, to movie *Blade Runner*'s quandary, and indirectly to our apathy to the question of who we are: "The paradox of self-consciousness is that it is possible only against the background of its own impossibility: I am conscious of myself only insofar as I am out of reach to myself qua the real kernel of my being ('I or he or it (the thing) which thinks')."⁷²

But Kant both defuses and escalates the enigma of the Cartesian subject. On the one hand, he seems to equate the I of pure apperception with the "noumenal Self" (the "Thing which thinks"). This has the effect of dusting off the empirical or substantial self from his philosophical dustbin as the appearance of the noumenal subject (or as how the noumenal self appears to itself in experiential phenomenon). On the other hand, he asserts that "in the synthetic original unity of apperception, I am conscious of myself, not as I appear to myself, nor as I am in myself, but only that I am,"⁷³ that is, neither noumenal nor phenomenal.⁷⁴ Zizek claims that Kant is compelled to define the "I" of transcendental apperception this way because of the "paradox of auto-affection: if I were given to myself phenomenally, as an object of experience, I would simultaneously have to be given to myself noumenally," which then dissolves the distinction.⁷⁵

Zizek argues that GWF Hegel radicalizes the Kantian split by being "thoroughly Kantian." This is because in Hegel's system, the Kantian status of the subject as neither noumenal or phenomenal also disintegrates the Kantian schema. To Zizek, Hegel's "absolute idealism" is nothing but the Kantian critique brought to its utmost consequences: 'there is no metalanguage; it is never possible for us to occupy the neutral place from which we could measure the distance that separates our semblance of knowledge from the In-itself of Truth.'⁷⁶ Is the "Absolute," thus, the solution wherein substance is also subject? Zizek asserts that this "subjectivization of the object" never really turns out in Hegel, as there is excess in the substance that escapes "subjective mediation." This excess is not an indication of failure or impediment but "correlative to the very being of the subject." Conversely, in the subjectivization of the substance, wherein it passes over into the "multitude of its particular predicates-determinations, the subject is precisely the void—"the empty form of a 'container,' which remains after all its content was 'subjectivized.'"⁷⁷

The obverse of these two modes of what remains (as phenomenal object and as noumenal subject) is the Hegelian subject of the impossible, of the "absolute, self-relating negativity"—negating and void. It is the zenith of the Cartesian subject cum Kantian transcendental subject. Returning to Kant, Zizek restates this in Jacques Lacan's equation of *fantasy* ("(\$ \bar{a})": 'I think' only insofar as I am inaccessible to myself qua noumenal Thing which thinks [the barred or split S]). The Thing is originally lost and the fantasy object (*a*) fills out its void.⁷⁷

To be a subject is to be conscious of the self as emptiness, the "night of the world." To be subject is to be continuously grasping at this emptiness. This is a moment of universality (of pure form) and freedom (of pure capacity to act). This is also a moment of failure, when the subject of the void (also the void in the chain of being) cannot accept its real and substitute instead Lacan's object (*a*) and thus constitute the fantasy of its putative identity.

⁷⁰ Zizek 1993, 12

⁷¹ Zizek 1993, 13

⁷² Zizek 1993, 15

⁷³ Quoted in Zizek 1993, 15

⁷⁴ Zizek 1993, 14

⁷⁵ Zizek 1993, 16

⁷⁶ Zizek 1993, 20

⁷⁷ Zizek 1993, 21

⁷⁸ Zizek 1993, 14